

Effects of Leadership and Innovation on Commitment and Performance of Employees

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Abstract

This research aims to analyze and describe the effects of leadership on commitment, innovation and performance, the effects of innovation on commitment and performance, the effects of commitment and performance as well as the role of commitment in mediating the effects of leadership and innovation on employee performance. As the samples, this research had 108 employees working in 42 community health centers consisting of 15 community health centers in Kendari city and 17 community health centers in Bau-Bau City, Southeast Sulawesi Province. Data collection technique was conducted by questionnaire distribution. This research used descriptive analysis in order to determine respondents' characteristics and respondents' description on the indicators of each research variable. Meanwhile, to test the pattern of inter-research variable effects, it used inferential analysis tool namely Structural Equation Modelling using WarpPLS approach. Results of this research showed that leadership had significant effects on commitment, innovation and performance, then innovation had positive and significant effects on commitment and performance as well as commitment had effects on performance. In addition, it was also found that commitment played a role in mediating the effects of leadership on employee performance and the effects of innovation on the employee performance working at community health centers in Southeast Sulawesi Province.

Keywords: *Commitment, Leadership, Innovation, Employee Performance.*

INTRODUCTION

Implementation of health service in public at primary level in Indonesia is by Community Health Center (CHC) as a unit of functional organization. Improvement of health service quality in CHC is increasingly important since the community is increasingly selective to obtain qualified health service, they as service users do not only pay but also demand good and qualified service ranging at the beginning until the final levels. Thus, the role of health personnel is required to provide professional service based on the main tasks and functions. All health facilities and infrastructure cannot be effective if it is not supported by good and professional medical personnel. Without reliable medical personnel, public health service cannot be optimal.

Community Health Center is one of the health technical implementation units beyond Regional Apparature Work Unit of Regency/City Health Office. In general, Community Health Center must have ability to provide preventive, promotive, curative services and also rehabilitative both by Individual Health Service or Public Health Service. To provide good service, it is certainly achieved by improvement of service quality in order to achieve optimal health level for all of the community (PMK No.75, 2014). Assessment of public opinions on service quality from government apparature is met by Public Satisfaction Index (PSI) which aims to determine service performance and is used as a standard to assess optimalization of public service performance given by government apparature to the community (the Law of Republic Indonesia No. 25, 2000).

Referring to the main task and functions of employees, it can be seen that the tasks given to the community health centers in Southeast Sulawesi Province by all of its problems face difficulties in its implementation. The process of achieving organizational goals based on main tasks and functions will be increasingly maximal if programmer performance can be appropriately achieved based on existing procedures. Less supporting or less effective programmer performance will distrust achievement of health service facility implementation. In reality, programmer performance in CHC in Southeast Sulawesi Province cannot be achieved based on the regulations which leads to less smooth work implementation effectively.

Phenomena of community health centers in Southeast Sulawesi Province show a number of problems related to Programmer Employee Performance. This can be seen by some problem indicators as follow: (a). It still can position service to others, employees, patients and also community as the number one service, (b). There are less optimal leaders in understanding each person with different abilities. As a result, the level of trust at leaders is strongly less optimal. And (c). there are also less commitment by CHC employees in providing services to patients, mainly for accident

victims, maternity patients and patients with various other diseases who need immediate help even though the slogan states that the service is open 24 hours.

Results of the observations by researchers at several community health centers in Southeast Sulawesi Province as these study objects found complaints about community health center programmers, the length of service delivery to service users due to internal and external constraints. Internal constraints include inadequate supporting equipment, low level of human resources quality and coordination between units. Inadequate facilities and infrastructure owned by agencies often distract the provision of services to service users.

Relatively low level of human resources quality increasingly distract the delivery of services to the community. The low level of human resources quality is indicated by officer inability to provide solutions to customers. Service is seen one of the spearheads of customer satisfaction efforts and is important to optimize it both by individuals and organizations, because the form of services provided reflects the quality of individuals or organizations as the service providers.

Regarding the results of research on improving Human Resources, especially leadership, there are still research gaps such as those studies conducted by Al, which found that leadership had no significant effect on employee performance. Another study on commitment. Any problem related to violating rules, such as absenteeism, leading to dismissal and resignation, is a form of lack of commitment to the company or organization. In this study, it can be seen that employees who have organizational commitment have positive effects.

Research gap which can be found in this research is triggers by former studies conducted by Al-Sada, Al-Esmael, and Faisal (2017) as well as Lok and Crawford (2004) which the research results show that innovative culture and supportive leadership style give significant effects on organizational commitment.

This research aims to analyze and describe the effects of leadership on commitment, innovation and performance, the effects of innovation on commitment and performance, the effects of commitment and performance as well as the role of commitment in mediating the effects of leadership and innovation on employee performance. Novelty in this research is development of conceptual model which is integrated by commitment aspects in mediating leadership and innovation effects on employee performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Leadership

Leadership is defined as ability of a leader to influence others by ways of triggering a sense of positive feeling within the people he or she leads in order to achieve any desired goals. Leadership is a process of influencing individual and group activities in the business in order to achieve certain goals and situation. (ANDAYANI and Soehari 2019) Leadership style has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Leaders must set an example so that employees can follow directions from superiors. Furthermore, the leadership element must pay attention to the variables that encourage performance and foster long-term relationships with employees so that employees are happy to come to work and have a desire to continue working in the organization. The efforts to influence many others are by communication to achieve goals. Five leadership functions commonly used as an indicators of research measurement, namely: (a). Instruction Function, (b). Consulting function, (c). Participation function, (d). Delegation function and e. Control function.

Innovation

Innovation is said to create added values, both in organization, shareholders, or broad community. The core of public sector innovation is to change an issue into a new one in order to improve efficiency and effectiveness in public sector organizations. Humaid ALMASKARI et al. (2021) explains that executives have a higher organizational status than workers, they will have more access to capital, which is a prerequisite for effective innovation. The results show that leaders who promote creativity will have a greater impact on employee innovation.

Commitment

Organizational commitment is the level to which an employee prioritizes an organization and its goals as well as desires to maintain membership in the organization (Robins, 2015). Organizational commitment means as a strong desire to remain as a member of a particular organization, a desire to give hard works in accordance with the wishes of the organization, as well as certain beliefs and acceptance of the organization values and goals. In other words, it is an attitude that reflects employee loyalty to the organization and a continuous process in which members of the organization show their concern for the organization and its success as well as continuous progress. 3 kinds of dimensions of organizational commitment, namely: (a). Affective Commitment, (b). Normative Commitment and (c). Continuing Commitment.

Performance

Performance is an illustration stating a level to which organizational success or failure in implementing main tasks and functions in order to realize targets, goals, vision and mission. In other words, performance is defined as achievement which can be achieved by organization in certain periods. Paais and Pattiruhu (2020) The results of the performance variable test show that employee performance is influenced by the leadership variable. leadership and organizational culture of employees need to be improved to improve performance. For evaluating employee performance consisting of six indicators including: (1) craft, (2) quantity and speed of completing work, (3) thoroughness or accuracy, (4) loyalty, (5) initiative, and (6) cooperation and ability to establish a working relationship.

Conceptual Framework

Based on the aforementioned literature review, a conceptual model was built which would be tested for its effect through this research. The explanation above can be summarized through the thinking framework that would be studied as follows:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Referring to the conceptual framework of the research above, it can be seen that employee performance is influenced by leadership including innovation, commitment. Then, there are also the roles of innovation, leadership and commitment on employee performance.

Research Hypotheses

Based on the aforementioned research conceptual framework, the hypotheses of this research are as follows:

- H1: Leadership has significant effects on commitment
- H2: Leadership has positive and significant effects on innovation
- H3: Leadership has positive and significant effects on performance
- H4: Employee innovation has positive and significant effects on commitment
- H5: Employee innovation has positive and significant effects on performance
- H6: Employee commitment has positive and significant effects on performance
- H7: Employee commitment has significant effects on mediating the effects of leadership on performance
- H8: Employee commitment has significant effects on mediating the effects of innovation on performance

METHOD

The population in this study were all Program Coordinators at 42 community health centers consisting of 15 Kendari City Community Health Centers and 17 Bau-Bau Community City Health Centers, Southeast Sulawesi Province with 11 community health centers each, so total population was 352 Program Coordinators. The number of samples was determined using slovin method with an estimator error (error rate) of 10% and the number of samples was 214 samples.

The type of data used in this study was primary data including data related to the respondents' statements on the variables of this study, namely leadership and performance dimensions of community health centers in Southeast Sulawesi. This primary data was obtained or sourced from the heads of community health centers by distributing direct questionnaires and in-depth interviews. In addition, it was supported by secondary data, namely data collection through relevant documents to this research study. The data analysis methods used in this study were descriptive analysis and structural equation testing (Structural Equation Modeling) or SEM through path coefficient analysis using SmartPLS version 3.0 software.

RESULTS

Testing of Structural Model (Inner Model)

Evaluation of the structural model with PLS can be started by determining the R-Square value for each endogenous latent variable as the predictive power of the structural model (Ghozali, 2012). After determining the R-Square values, then it can determine the T-Statistics value in the Path Coefficients table of each variable to be compared with the T-table which can then be used as a reference in hypothesis testing.

Changes in the R-Square value can be used to explain the effects of certain exogenous latent variables (X) on endogenous latent variables (Y) whether they have substantive effects or not. The R-Square value of 0.70 indicates the model is at a strong level, 0.50 indicates the model is at a moderate level, and 0.25 indicates the model is at a weak level (Ghozali, 2012). Here are the R-Square values in the construct:

Tabel 1. R-Square

Construct	R-Square
Innovation	0.881
Commitment	0.822
Employee Performance	0.891

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2021

Based on table 1, the R-Square value of the effects of the leadership construct (X1) on innovation is 0.881. The effect of leadership (X1) and innovation (Y1) constructs on commitment is 0.822. The effect of leadership (X1), innovation (Y1), and commitment (Y2) constructs on performance is 0.891. All of these R-square values are at a strong level, which means that the effect of leadership (X1), innovation (Y1) and commitment (Y2) on employee performance (Y3) is 89.1%. Therefore, it can be concluded that the performance variable can be explained by the leadership, innovation, and commitment variables of 89.1% while the remaining is influenced by other variables excluded in this study.

Hypothesis Test

The procedure in testing the hypotheses is by comparing the value of T-statistics with T-table. A hypothesis is said to be accepted if the T- statistics is greater (>) than the T-table. To determine the value of the degree of freedom (df), the researchers use the aggregate formula (nk) which n = many observations while k = the number of variables (dependant and independent) so that nk = 108-4 = 104, so that the T-table value is 1,983 in significance level 5% (0.05). This T-table value will then be compared with the T-statistical value in the Path Coefficient table after the bootstrapping process is carried out. To clarify the process of testing the following hypothesis, an image of the bootstrapping results is presented:

Figure 2 Bootstrapping Model

Based on the results of the bootstrapping process as shown in Figure 2 above, the path coefficient values in this research model can be presented in table 2 below:

Table 2 Path Coefficients (Mean, STDEV, t-Values)

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	t Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Leadership → Commitment	0.617	0.615	0.129	4.763	0.000
Leadership → innovation	0.938	0.935	0.023	40.996	0.000
Leadership → Performance	0.496	0.501	0.113	4.376	0.000
Innovation → Commitment	0.303	0.301	0.131	2.305	0.022
Innovation → Performance	0.227	0.223	0.107	2.121	0.034
Commitment → Performance	0.248	0.245	0.075	3.295	0.001

PLS Output Results

- If the t-statistic value is greater than the t-table value then, there is a significant effect
- If the t-statistic value is smaller than the t-table value then, there is no significant effect

The results of the path analysis test in the results of this study can be seen in table 3.

1. Effects of Leadership on Organizational Commitment

The first hypothesis proposed in this study is “Leadership has positive and significant effects on the commitment of community health center employees in Southeast Sulawesi Province”. Table 5.3 shows the original sample estimate between the effects of leadership on organizational commitment of 0.617 and has a positive value. The P-Value value of 4.763 is greater than the t-table of 1.983. This value indicates that leadership has positive and significant effects on organizational commitment.

2. Effects of Leadership on Innovation

The second hypothesis proposed in this study is “Leadership has positive and significant effects on the innovation of community health center employees in Southeast Sulawesi Province”. Table 5.3 shows the original sample estimate between the effects of leadership on innovation of 0.938 and has a positive value. The P-Value value of 40.996 is greater than the t-table of 1.983. This value indicates that leadership has positive and significant effects on innovation.

3. Effects of Leadership on Employee Performance

The third hypothesis proposed in this study is “Leadership has positive and significant effects on the performance of community health center employees in Southeast Sulawesi Province”. Table 5.3 shows the original sample estimate between the effects of leadership on employee performance of 0.496 and has a positive value. The P-Value value of 4.376 is greater than the t-table of 1.983. This value indicates that leadership has positive and significant effects on employee performance.

4. Effects of Employee Innovation on Employee Commitment

The fourth hypothesis proposed in this study is “Employee innovation has positive and significant effects on the commitment of community health center employees in Southeast Sulawesi Province”. Table 5.15 shows the original sample estimate between the effects of employee innovation on organizational commitment of 0.303 and has a positive value. The P-Value value of 2.305 is greater than the t-table of 1.983. This value indicates that innovation of community health center employees has positive and significant effects on organizational commitment.

5. Effects of Employee Innovation on Employee Performance

The fifth hypothesis proposed in this study is “Employee Innovation has positive and significant effects on the performance of community health center employees in Southeast Sulawesi Province”. Table 5.15 shows the original sample estimate between the effects of employee innovation on employee performance of 0.227 and has a positive value. The P-Value value of 2.121 is greater than the t-table of 1.983. This value indicates that innovation of community health center employees has positive and significant effects on employee performance.

6. Effects of Employee Commitment on Employee Performance

The sixth hypothesis proposed in this study is “Employee Commitment has positive and significant effects on the performance of community health center employees in Southeast Sulawesi Province”. Table 5.15 shows the original sample estimate between the effects of commitment on organizational employee performance of **0.248** and has a positive value. The P-Value value of **3.295** is greater than the t-table of **1.983**. This value indicates that commitment of community health center employees has positive and significant effects on employee performance. Thus, the sixth hypothesis is **accepted** meaning that higher community health center employee commitment to implement the community health center programs will lead to increasingly higher level of community health center employee performance.

To test the mediating effect between the variables in this study, it can be done by determining the values in the Specific Indirect Effect table and the p-value in the Total Indirect Effect table. If the p-value on the indirect effect is less than 0.01 then it can be said that the intervening variable in the study has a significant effect in being a mediator between the variables.

Table 3 Indirect Effects

Mediation Path	Specific Indirect Effects
Leadership → Commitment → Performance	0.153
Innovation → Commitment → Performance	0.075

Table 4 Total Indirect Effect

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Leadership → Performance	0.153	0.150	0.054	2.822	0.005
Innovation → Performance	0.075	0.074	0.041	1.813	0.070

Based on tables 5.4 and 5.5, it can be explained that the roles of commitment in mediating the effects of leadership on employee performance and the role of commitment in mediating the effects of innovation on employee performance are as follows:

- H₇ The seventh hypothesis proposed in this study is “Commitment mediates the effects of leadership on the performance of community health center employees in Southeast Sulawesi Province”. The results in tables 5.16 and 5.17 show that the indirect effect of leadership on performance through commitment (0.153) has a t-statistic value of 2.822 with a p-value smaller than 0.01 (0.005). Based on this, it can be said that employee commitment has significant effects to become a mediator variable on the effects of leadership on employee performance.
- H₈ The eighth hypothesis proposed in this study is “Commitment mediates the effects of innovation on the performance of community health center employees in Southeast Sulawesi Province”. The results in tables 5.4 and 5.5 show that the indirect effect of innovation on performance through organizational commitment (0.153) has a t-statistic value of 1.813 with a p-value greater than 0.01 (0.005). Based on this, it can be said that employee commitment has significant effects to become a mediator variable on the effects of innovation on employee performance.

DISCUSSION

Direct Effects of Leadership on Organizational Commitment

Based on the research result show that leadership with indicators: instructive behavior, consultative behavior, participatory behavior and delegative behavior have direct effects on organizational commitment perceived by the coordinator staff of the community health center programs in Southeast Sulawesi Province. However, from the detection of employee answers to organizational commitment, there are still employees who perceive that all indicators are smaller than leadership but are still in the good category in carrying out service activities and employees must be able to understand that in carrying out service activities, there will always be priority..

Effects of Leadership on Innovation

Based on the research result of leadership direct effects on innovation, it is obtained positive and significant path coefficient value showing that leadership has effects on innovation. Positive path coefficient means the existence of unidirectional relationship between leadership and innovation. Higher level of leadership in community health center in Southeast Sulawesi Province will lead to higher level of work innovation. This research results are in line with former research Hülya G.C, and Gönül KO (2016), showing that understanding the relationship between transformational leadership and creativity facilitates leaders to develop and encourage capacity of employee creativity or performance.

Effects of Leadership on Employee Performance

Based on the research result of direct effects of leadership variable on employee performance, it is obtained positive and significant path coefficient value showing that leadership has effects on performance. Positive path coefficient means the existence of unidirectional relationship between leadership and performance. Higher level of leadership in community health center in Southeast Sulawesi Province will lead to higher level of employee performance. The results of this study are in line with the research of Pancasila, Haryono, and Sulistyono (2020) that the policy to improve employee performance is that management focuses more on increasing leadership capacity. Suggestions for organizations in

improving employee performance to prioritize increasing job satisfaction, through leadership because the path in the research model shows the most significant total effect.

Effects of Employee Innovation on Employee Commitment

Based on the research result of direct effects of employee innovation on employee commitment working in the community health center in Southeast Sulawesi Province, it is obtained positive and significant path coefficient value showing employee innovation significant effects on employee commitment. Positive path coefficient means the existence of unidirectional relationship between employee innovation and employee commitment. Higher level of innovation in community health center in Southeast Sulawesi Province will lead to higher level of organizational commitment. This research result empirically proves that innovation with 4 indicators namely looking at opportunities, expressing ideas, struggling and application give direct effects on organizational commitment as perceived by the program coordinator employees of community health center in Southeast Sulawesi Province.

Effects of Employee Innovation on Employee Performance

Based on the research result of direct effects of employee innovation on employee performance, it is obtained positive and significant path coefficient value showing employee innovation significant effects on employee performance. Positive path coefficient means the existence of unidirectional relationship between employee innovation and employee performance. Higher level of innovation in community health center in Southeast Sulawesi Province will lead to higher level of employee performance. Defined innovation as new idea applied to initiate or improve a product or process and service.

Effects of Employee Commitment on Employee Performance

Based on the direct effects of employee commitment on employee performance, it is obtained positive and significant path coefficient value showing employee commitment effects on employee performance. Positive path coefficient means the existence of unidirectional relationship between employee commitment and employee performance. Higher level of employee commitment in community health center in Southeast Sulawesi Province will lead to higher level of employee performance. In their research, Whipple and Frankel (2000) also proven that the existence of senior management support plays an important factor to determine the success of strategy alliance. The results of this study are in line with research by (ASTUTY and UDIN 2020) that employee commitment has a significant effect on employee performance, the higher the employee's commitment, the performance will increase.

Effects of Leadership on Employee Performance Working in Community Health Centers in Southeast Sulawesi Province Mediated by Commitment

Based on the analysis results on the effects of leadership on the employee performance working in community health centers in Southeast Sulawesi Province, which is mediated by commitment, it can be seen that employee commitment has significant effects as being a mediator variable on the effects of leadership on employee performance. Therefore, it can be explained that the employee commitment at the community health centers in Southeast Sulawesi Province as a mediating variable, which is measured through 3 indicators, including indicators of affective, normative and continuity can mediate the effects of leadership on the employee performance at the community health centers in Southeast Sulawesi Province..

Effects of Innovation on Employee Performance at Community Health Centers in Southeast Sulawesi Province Mediated by Commitment

Commitment to mediate the effects of innovation on the employee performance at community health centers in Southeast Sulawesi Province or in another sense, the indirect effects of innovation on performance through organizational commitment shows positive and significant so that it can be said that organizational commitment has significant effects as being a mediator variable on the effects of innovation on employee performance. Results of this study state that commitment can strengthen the effects of innovation on the employee performance at community health centers in Southeast Sulawesi Province. Thus, it can be explained that commitment serves as a perfect mediation variable (pure mediation).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of analysis, hypothesis testing, and discussion of research on the Role of Commitment in Mediating the Effects of Leadership and Innovation on the Performance of Community Health Center Employees in Southeast Sulawesi Province, the following conclusions can be drawn: (1). Leadership has positive and significant effects on the employee commitment working at community health centers, (2). Leadership has positive and significant effects on

employee innovation, (3). Leadership has positive and significant effects on employee performance, (4). Employee innovation has positive and significant effects on employee commitment, (5). Employee innovation has positive and significant effects on employee performance (6). Employee commitment has positive and significant effects on performance, (7). Commitment mediates the effects of leadership on employee performance and (8). Commitment mediates the positive and significant effects of innovation on the employee performance working at community health centers in Southeast Sulawesi Province. Based on these conclusions, it can be said that organizational commitment has significant effects as being a mediator variable on the effects of innovation on employee performance.

Referring to the research discussion and conclusion, then the recommendation which can be given in this research is to realize innovation by always giving priority to create new methods, spend effective time and have orientation to actions and create employee involvement in the organization through employee emotional attachment with the organization. Also, further research can provide generalization of leadership effects on employee performance by commitment mediation by adding research variables such as work satisfaction and competence variables.

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